

First record of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) for Switzerland

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ABSTRACT: The first record of the Nearctic assassin bug species *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae: Harpactorini) for Switzerland is reported. The European distribution of the species is discussed.

KEYWORDS: *Zelus renardii*, invasive species, first record, distribution, Switzerland, Europe.

The leafhopper assassin bug *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae: Harpactorini) is an invasive Nearctic species which established stable populations in various countries of the Mediterranean Region (Kment & van der Heyden, 2022).

Recently, *Z. renardii* expanded its European distribution northwards from the Mediterranean Region, crossing the Alps (van der Heyden, 2023). Single specimens were found in Austria (van der Heyden & Staudinger, 2023) and in

Germany (van der Heyden, 2021a, 2021b, 2023). Apparently introduced specimens were reported also from other countries: Belarus, Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, Great Britain, the Netherlands (van der Heyden, 2021a, 2021b; Kment & van der Heyden, 2022; Lukashuk et al. 2022; Claerebout & Lock, 2023; Aukema & Schets, 2024).

Taking the recent spread of *Z. renardii* into account, the first observation of the species in Switzerland has been expected. Now, the first record of *Z. renardii* in the country can be reported:

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On 03.08.2024, an adult specimen (Fig. 1) was found and photographed in the Botanical Garden of the University of Zurich (Nadja Baumgartner, pers. comm.). Two related photos were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Baumgartner, 2024).

Figure 1. Specimen of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857, Zurich, Switzerland, 03.08.2024. (Photo: Nadja Baumgartner).

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